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Addressing the Needs of High-Achieving and Highly Able Students in Literacy and Numeracy

A Review of the Research

Prepared by Gerry Shiel and Vasiliki Pitsia, Educational Research Centre,
for the Department of Education

Author Note

Gerry Shiel <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6491-9532>

Vasiliki Pitsia <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8172-0397>

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Summary

The results of recent international assessments in which Ireland has participated, including PIRLS 2016 and TIMSS 2019 (Grade 4), and PISA 2018 (15-year olds) suggest that the proportions of highly-able students are broadly along expected lines for reading literacy (given Ireland's average performance, as well as performance relative to other countries), and below expectations for mathematics (and science) (Pitsia & Lysaght, 2021). In PISA 2018 mathematics, just 8.2% of students in Ireland performed at the highest proficiency levels (Levels 5-6), compared to an OECD average of 10.9%, despite Ireland's above average performance in mathematics. Although there is now broad recognition by educational authorities of the need to raise the performance of high achievers in Ireland, with the establishment of specific targets in the Interim Review of the National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy (DES, 2017a), no concrete initiatives have been put in place within education system to raise standards, other than those related to curriculum development in general, and then mainly at Junior Cycle (Pitsia & Lysaght, 2021). They note that lack adequate provision militates against efforts to build the type of knowledge society that Ireland aspires to become (e.g., Government of Ireland, 2018), which requires cohorts of strong performers in mathematics and other STEM subjects (science, technology, and engineering). Underperformance in mathematics is particularly problematic, given that proficiency in mathematics can drive performance in other STEM subjects.

A number of authors have defined the characteristics of highly-able students. In literacy, these include high levels of engagement, monitoring of reading comprehension, access to linguistically rich texts, and deployment of a range of strategies in response to the particular demands of texts (Abilock, 1999). In numeracy, they include ability to think logically and symbolically about qualitative and spatial relationships, ability to perceive and generalise about mathematical patterns, structures, relations and operations, and flexibility and reversibility of mental processes in mathematical activity (House, 1987, cited in Bicknell, 2008). Pitsia (2021) examined variables associated with high achievement in international assessments. Drawing on the data for PISA 2018 mathematics in Ireland, she used multi-level modelling to identify variables associated with high achievement (performance at Levels 5-6). Variables that were positively associated with performance included economic, social and cultural status (the PISA variable for SES), self-efficacy in mathematics and openness to problem solving. Anxiety about mathematics was negatively associated with high achievement.

Although services are provided for gifted students in mathematics and related areas by entities such as the Centre for Talented Youth, Ireland at Dublin City University, these typically involve relatively small proportions of students, usually the strongest performers on tests of general ability. While many students involved in the work of CTY-Ireland are also likely to perform strongly in reading literacy and mathematics, there is a larger group, comprising of about 10%-15% of students, who are high achievers, or have the potential for high achievement in literacy and numeracy. The performance of high achievers needs to increase, and more students need to move into the high achiever bracket, especially in mathematics. This needs to occur early, and it needs to continue through post-primary schooling. A two-pronged approach is required – one focusing on extending the performance of higher-achieving students, and the other on raising overall standards at national level. The challenge in raising overall standards is underlined by the fact that average performance on PISA mathematics in Ireland in 2018 was similar to 2003, 2006, 2012 and 2015 (i.e., despite the implementation of Project Maths in all schools from 2010 onwards and the carrot of bonus CAO points).

There is limited evidence on the effectiveness of interventions to support high-achieving and/or gifted students, especially those living in disadvantaged circumstances (Montacute, 2018). In their systematic reviews of the effectiveness of interventions designed to accelerate performance, several researchers did not report on effect sizes because of concerns about the quality of the studies they had reviewed (see García-Martínez et al., 2021; Bailey et al., 2012), with general principles underpinning effective interventions presented instead.

Where disadvantage is concerned, four approaches to supporting highly-able students were identified by Cullen et al. (2018) in England – academic extension, cultural enrichment, personal development, and the removal of financial barriers to achievement. Cullen et al. also emphasised the importance of strong leadership, and implementation of a strategic focus for those with the potential for high achievement.

García-Martínez et al. (2021) identified a variety of didactic strategies and models designed to meet the needs of gifted students, including acceleration, enrichment and extension programmes. They also noted a pressing need for research on the effectiveness of individualised adaptations focusing on the needs and interests of gifted students (rather than the implementation of generalised approaches). Bailey et al. (2012) focused on the different settings in which gifted students were offered support, and concluded that in-school programmes were likely to be more effective than external programmes, such as special schools for gifted and talented students. Among the in-school programmes were streamed classes (such as classes at a higher grade level) that provided G & T students with an enriched learning

environment adapted to their needs (a ‘vertical curriculum’ approach), and mixed ability classes, where differentiated activities were provided for G & T students. Bailey et al. also noted the value of teaching specific strategies to enhance gifted and talented students’ learning and engagement, such as self-regulation and higher-order thinking skills, and the key role of teachers in generating and sustaining the social contexts in which gifted and talented students learn. In her meta-analysis, Kim (2015) reported that enrichment programmes, which typically focused on teaching higher-order skills, had a strong average effect (0.96) on performance in areas such as reading literacy and mathematics. After the exclusion of one problematic study, Steenbergen-Hu and Moon (2011) reported an effect size (g) of 0.18 for acceleration programmes, which included early kindergarten/school/college entrance, subject matter acceleration, advanced placement and curriculum compacting, though the authors noted that none of these had been unambiguously defined.

Specific strategies that have been implemented in effective literacy and numeracy programmes for highly-able students include use of more complex texts and an emphasis on inferencing and higher-order thinking skill to improve critical thinking in literacy, a strong focus on real-life problem solving in numeracy, and the development of self-regulation and metacognitive skills as cross-curricular skills. The use of ICTs has not, as yet, featured strongly in the literature on supporting highly-able students, though this may reflect a time lag between the publication of individual studies and the subsequent publication of systematic reviews.

Recommendations

Given the nature of high achievement, and the fact that highly-able students are unlikely to be evenly spread across schools and classrooms, it is likely that a range of strategies will need to be implemented to raise performance in literacy, numeracy and related areas (e.g., science).

Pillar 1: Enabling parents and communities to support children’s literacy and numeracy development

- Parents should be involved identifying highly-able students, and in supporting them to reach their potential, in partnership with schools (Cullen et al., 2018; Montacute, 2018).

Pillar 3: Building the capacity for school leadership

- Principals and school leaders should be supported in identifying and providing interventions for highly-able students, and those with the potential for high achievement, in all schools, include those that are socioeconomically disadvantaged. Programmes that are implemented should be monitored, reviewed and evaluated by school leaders to ensure that they benefit highly-able students (Cullen et al., 2018).

Pillar 4: Curriculum and the learning experience

- Schools and teachers should be supported in implementing a range of interventions both to extend the performance of highly-able students in literacy and numeracy, and to increase the proportions of those with high achievement. Measures to raise the performance of high achievers should include enrichment activities within the context of current curricula, differentiation, programmes tailored to individual students' needs, acceleration and mentoring (Bailey et al., 2012; García-Martínez et al., 2021; Kim, 2016; Steenbergen-Hu & Moon, 2021).
- Stronger, more focused efforts should be made to raise overall standards in mathematics, as this is likely to result in an increase in the proportion of high-achieving students. Data from TIMSS mathematics at primary level and PISA mathematics at post-primary level suggest that there is considerable scope for raising overall standards in mathematics (Mullis et al., 2020; OECD, 2019).

Pillar 5: Students with Additional Learning Needs

- Students with high achievement in literacy and/or numeracy at primary level, including those in DEIS schools, should be tracked at post-primary level to ensure that they are supported in reaching their potential (Montacute, 2018).
- Efforts should also be made to increase the proportions of students from under-represented groups among high achievers in literacy and numeracy. These include students with low socioeconomic status, female students, those with ethnic minority status and dual exceptionality students.

Pillar 6: Assessment and evaluation to support learning in literacy and numeracy

- The assessment of high achievement in literacy and numeracy should be based on performance on standardised measures of achievement in these areas (Montacute, 2018). In the case of mathematics, attention should also be given to performance on measures of spatial reasoning, as well as measures of confidence and/or anxiety.

- The observations of teachers and parents should also be taken into account in identifying children with high achievement, or the potential for high achievement (Cullen al., 2018).
- Where hard cut-off points are used to identify highly-able students (e.g., those eligible for support programmes), allowances should be made for low-SES students who may have unrealised potential for high achievement (Montacute, 2018).

Addressing the Needs of Higher-Achieving Students

This report addresses two issues in relation to high achieving students: identification and supports. First, definitions and identification are considered. The second section addresses intervention, including evidence of effectiveness, based on a literature search of recent systematic reviews. A note on provision and policy in Ireland is provided in the final section. The focus of this paper is on two overlapping groups of students, those who are described as gifted and talented, and those who are described as high achievers in literacy and numeracy. The performance of these groups is of interest because of the relative underperformance of higher-achieving students in Ireland in recent national and international assessments of mathematics (and science) (e.g., Pitsia & Lysaght, 2021).

Definitions of High Achievement and Characteristics of High Achievers

A range of terms is used in the research literature to refer to high-performing students, including gifted, talented, more able, highly able, very able, high ability, especially able, highly capable, high attaining, exceptionally able and creative. According to Bailey et al. (2012), the terminology used differs across education systems, with, for example, ‘gifted and talented’ used in England, ‘more able’ in Scotland, and ‘talented’ and ‘more able’ in Wales.

The UK’s Department of Children, Schools and Families (2007, p. 1) defined gifted and talented as ‘those who have one or more abilities developed to a level significantly ahead of their peer group (or with the potential to develop these abilities)’. The DCSF (2007) makes a distinction between ‘gifted’ and ‘talented’ students in terms of the curriculum areas in which they excel: the former relates to high ability in academic subjects such as English or Mathematics; the latter in areas requiring visio-spatial skills or practical abilities, such as games, physical education, drama or art. García-Martínez et al. (2021) note that giftedness (or high-ability, their preferred term) can now be viewed as a multi-dimensional construct that

includes several characteristics of the individual, including high general cognitive ability , academic achievement, creativity and motivation.

Gifted and talented students can also be described with reference to their characteristics. Renzulli's (1988) three-ringed conception of giftedness focused on above average ability, task commitment and creativity. Renzulli also made a distinction between giftedness based on high performance on tests of cognitive ability, and creative-productive giftedness, which he describes as involving the application of previously-learned information or content to new domains. According to Renzulli, both high-achievement and creative-productive giftedness can be found in the same individual. Gardner (1993) described eight intelligences in his theory of multiple intelligences, implying that a student could be gifted in one or more of the verbal linguistic, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinaesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal and naturalistic domains.

Sternberg et al. (2010) incorporated previous research to devise the Pentagonal Theory for Identifying the Gifted that outlines 5 criteria. The excellence criterion states that an individual ought to show greater capabilities in more than one domain compared to peers of the same age group. The value criterion states an individual should be excellent in activities valued by the society they live in. The level of excellence should be rare and lead to productive outcomes (i.e., scoring high on a test does not result necessarily in productivity). In addition, to determine giftedness, a person should demonstrate their ability on a variety of tests. The implication of this theory is that scoring well on an intelligence test may help with one's academic progress, but unless it is transformed into a productive skill, it may not affect one's future life outcomes. Therefore, an individual who shows potential should not only foster their cognitive skills, but also their psychosocial capabilities to adapt to rapidly changing environments (e.g., family, work, spouses, among others.).

Prior to 2010, the UK Government implemented supports in schools for gifted and talented students, including streaming, accelerated learning, master classes, specialist classes on a subject, normally delivered by an expert in the field, and extra school trips. Gifted and talented students were identified as being in the top 5% nationally (based on their Key Stage 2 scores at the end of primary schooling); were gifted relative to peers in their year group and school/college; were talented at non-academic subjects; or had high potential, even if they had not yet translated that potential into high achievement (Department for Children, Schools and Families, 2008). According to Montacute (2018), the DCSF's definition was problematic in that the percentage identified as gifted and talented ranged from 0% in some schools to 100% in others; only a weak link was found between students identified as gifted and

talented, and those who went on to attend selective universities; and the percentage of gifted and talented students in a school had very little relation to how students in the school performed on national tests. Montacute concluded that the broad definition of gifted and talented resulted in the programme having mixed impact.

Hazma et al. (2020) note that low-income and minority gifted students in the UK are under-identified and are, therefore, under-represented in the gifted population, giving rise to an 'excellence gap'. The authors argue that those from lower income areas are at a disadvantage because they attend schools with less-qualified teachers and may be exposed to more punitive and exclusionary discipline. Such students may also have fewer opportunities to attend extracurricular activities that will foster informal learning.

Montacute (2018) defined the highly-able as those students performing in the top 10% nationally in English and mathematics at the end of primary schooling (end of Key Stage 2). However, she also distinguished between highly-able students as students with high attainment and those with the potential for high attainment (such as those who performed well in the early years of primary education), reflecting a concern about harnessing the potential of low- and moderate SES students, who may otherwise be lost to higher education and the professions. According to Montacute, only 4% of disadvantaged students have high attainment at Key Stage 2, compared to 13% of non-disadvantaged pupils. Moreover, in general, disadvantaged students fall further behind their non-disadvantaged counterparts over the early years of secondary education. Montacute also warns that teachers may not be the best persons to identify highly-able students, as they may be biased towards certain groups (females, ethnic minorities, ESL etc.) and hence recommends the use of tests as well as teacher judgements. However, she qualifies this by stating that, where a hard cut-off point is used, schools should consider reducing the boundary for students from disadvantaged backgrounds, to reflect the likely impact of the attainment gap between disadvantaged and non-disadvantaged groups, and the extent to which this can mask potential. In Ireland, Smyth et al. (2015) note a high level of ability grouping in DEIS post-primary schools, and a need to ensure that students in such schools did not reach a decision on whether or not to take subjects at Higher level in the Leaving Certificate exam until as late a point as possible.

Figure 1: Selected Descriptions of High Performance in International Assessments of Reading Literacy and Mathematics

PIRLS Grade 4 (Mullis et al., 2017) – Advanced Benchmark

When reading relatively complex *literary texts*, students can:

- Interpret story events and character actions to describe reasons, motivations, feelings and character development with full text-based support
- Begin to evaluate the effect on the reader of the author’s language and style choices.

When reading relatively complex *informational texts*, students can

- Distinguish and interpret complex information in different parts of a text, and provide full text-based support
- Integrate information across a text to explain relationships and sequence activities
- Begin to evaluate visual and textual elements to consider the author’s point of view.

PISA Reading Literacy (OECD, 2019) – Level 6 (Highest benchmark)*

Readers at Level 6 can comprehend lengthy and abstract texts in which the information of interest is deeply embedded and only indirectly related to the task. They can compare, contrast and integrate information representing multiple and potentially conflicting perspectives, using multiple criteria and generating inferences across distant pieces of information to determine how the information may be used. Readers at Level 6 can reflect deeply on the text’s source in relation to its content, using criteria external to the text. They can compare and contrast information across texts, identifying and resolving inter-textual discrepancies and conflicts through inferences about the sources of information, their explicit or vested interests, and other cues as to the validity of the information. Tasks at Level 6 typically require the reader to set up elaborate plans, combining multiple criteria and generating inferences to relate the task and the text(s). Materials at this level include one or several complex and abstract text(s), involving multiple and possibly discrepant perspectives. Target information may take the form of details that are deeply embedded within or across texts and potentially obscured by competing information.

TIMSS Grade 4 (Mullis et al., 2020) – Advanced Benchmark

Students can apply their understanding and knowledge in a variety of relatively complex situations and explain their reasoning. Students can solve a variety of multistep word problems involving whole numbers and show an understanding of fractions and decimals. They can apply knowledge of two- and three-dimensional shapes in a variety of situations. Students can interpret and represent data to solve multistep problems.

PISA Mathematical Literacy (OECD, 2019) – Level 6 (Highest benchmark)*

At Level 6, students can conceptualise, generalise and utilise information based on their investigations and modelling of complex problem situations, and can use their knowledge in relatively non-standard contexts. They can link different information sources and representations together and flexibly translate amongst them. Students at this level are capable of advanced mathematical thinking and reasoning. These students can apply this insight and understanding, along with a mastery of symbolic and formal mathematical operations and relationships, to develop new approaches and strategies for attacking novel situations. Students at this level can reflect on their actions, and can formulate and precisely communicate their actions and reflections regarding their findings, interpretations, arguments and the appropriateness of these to the original situation.

*Readers are also referred to descriptors of proficiency level 5 for PISA reading literacy and mathematics, as PISA defines high-achievers as those performing at Levels 5 or 6.

International studies provide some insights into the characteristics of high performers in reading literacy and mathematics. Figure 1 provides descriptions of top performers in reading literacy and mathematics in recent studies.

These indicators of proficiency are mirrored in descriptions of high performers in mathematics. For example, Bicknell (2008) cites House (1987) as describing the skills of high achievers in mathematics as:

- Early curiosity and understanding about the quantitative aspect of things
- Ability to think logically and symbolically about quantitative and spatial relationships
- Ability to perceive and generalise about mathematical patterns, structures, relations and operations
- Ability to reason analytically, inductively and deductively
- Ability to abbreviate mathematical reasoning, and to find rational economical solutions
- Flexibility and reversibility of mental processes in mathematical activity
- Ability to remember mathematical symbols, relationships, proofs and methods of solution
- Ability to transfer learning to novel situations
- Energy and persistence in solving mathematical problems, and
- Mathematical perception of the world.

The international literature also provides information on the skills of high-achieving or gifted readers. For example, prior to widespread access to electronic reading, Abilock (1999) noted that:

- High-achieving readers are skilled, flexible readers who read often
- They monitor their reading
- They benefit from reading linguistically rich texts
- They deploy a range of skills in response to particular demands of a text
- They are passionate readers who find books to love.

According to Catron and Wingenbach (1986), gifted readers use the following skills:

- They anticipate meaning based on visual clues in the text
- They use prior knowledge and experience, personal identification and reader purpose
- They are aware of how to process texts for information/concept gathering.
- They establish links between the present text and what they have previously read, and, as a result, concepts are formed or developed.

The characteristics and skills of gifted readers observed by Abilock and by Catron and Wingenbach are consistent with those referenced in the descriptions of high-achievers in literacy at primary level (PIRLS) and post-primary level (PISA). While lists such as these can be useful for mapping out the skills that lower-achieving readers need to attain, they may also be useful for setting literacy-related tasks for higher-achieving students, or identifying when particular skills have been achieved on texts of appropriate difficulty, prior to deciding to accelerate performance.

It might also be noted that the skills specific to high achievement and/or giftedness in mathematics and reading may be linked to more generic skills that are deployed by these students across domains. According to a report on gifted education published by the New South Wales Department of Education (2019),

- Gifted students' brains can have a similar level of operational function to older students
- Advanced neural development in the brains of students is associated with measures of intelligence and general ability
- Gifted students can often apply more cognitive resources to thinking and learning processes
- Gifted individuals can typically apply their advanced thinking and learning skills across a range of areas
- Advanced brain development can include differences such as denser grey matter, greater surface area and neural activation, faster neural efficiency, and greater plasticity.

According to the NSW Department of Education (2019), these characteristics justify the need for advanced content, greater speed, and more complexity in learning tasks for gifted students when compared to students the same age, as such students have. . .

- the potential for greater analytical depth (a key factor in effective reading comprehension)
- the ability to process information, thought and learning in a faster or more efficient manner, requiring fewer repetitions for mastery
- greater capability in a range of cognitive skills, such as fluid reasoning, creative thinking, memory and abstract reasoning

- the ability to make inter-subject connections with relative ease and seek ‘top-down’ understanding when learning.

Pitsia (2021) conducted a study of the characteristics of high-achieving students in Ireland on national and international studies of mathematics (and science) using hierarchical two-level binary logistic regression models. Two models are of interest here – one relating to mathematics at primary level (TIMSS 2015, Grade 4) and one relating to mathematics at post-primary level (PISA 2012¹, 15-year olds). In implementing the regression models, student and family demographics were entered in the first step, followed by student self-beliefs, dispositions, drive and engagement (step 2), student mathematics-related activities and schedule, parents’ dispositions and support (step 3), mathematics learning at school (step 4), and, finally, school/classroom characteristics (step 5). In effect, the characteristics of high-performing students (those performing at the Advanced level in TIMSS at Grade 4) and (separately) those performing at Levels 5-6 on PISA mathematics are compared with those of students performing below the Advanced level on TIMSS or below Levels 5-6 on PISA.

After accounting for other predictors in the PISA 2012 model, four student-level variables and no variables at school level were significantly associated with the odds of students being high achievers in mathematics in the final model. For each unit or standard deviation increase in students’ family economic, social and cultural status (the PISA ESCS measure), students were 87% more likely to belong to the high-achieving group in mathematics, compared to the non-high-achieving group (Odds Ratio = 1.87). An increase of one unit in the student mathematics anxiety index was associated with a 47% decrease in the likelihood of being a high achiever in mathematics (OR = 0.53). Students were 2.2 times more likely to be high achievers with each unit increase in mathematics self-efficacy (OR = 2.22) and they had a 55% greater chance of high achievement in mathematics for each unit increase in student openness to problem solving (OR = 1.55). Other variables under consideration were not significant in the final model, including instrumental motivation, interest in mathematics, mathematics work ethic, disciplinary climate in mathematics classrooms, and school average ESCS and school size. In all, the variables in the final model explained 41.8% of the variance in high achievement in mathematics at student level, and 36.4% at school level.

¹ 2012 represents the last PISA cycle in which mathematics was a major assessment domain prior to writing this paper. A further assessment takes place in 2022.

In the case of TIMSS at Grade 4, five student-level variables, and no variables at the school/class level predicted students' membership of the high achievement (Advanced level) group. Non-attendance by students at extra mathematics lessons was the strongest predictor of fourth-graders' high achievement in mathematics, with students who reported that they did not attend extra mathematics lessons being 3.19 times more likely to be high achievers compared to those who did attend extra lessons (OR = 3.19). Students' odds of being high achievers were expected to increase by 34% for every additional unit in the TIMSS home resources for learning index (OR = 1.34). Students with higher confidence in mathematics were expected to increase their odds of being high achievers by 41% per unit increase on the index (OR = 1.41), while students who were able to do literacy tasks when they began primary school (according to their parents) were expected to have increased odds, by 39% (OR = 1.39). Infrequency of computer/tablet use for schoolwork at home was also a significant predictor of high achievement, with students who reported using computers/tablets for schoolwork at home 'never or almost never' or 'once or twice a month' being about twice as likely to be high achievers in mathematics, compared to those who reported using them 'every day or almost every day' (ODs = 2.06, 1.82, respectively), perhaps reflecting a practice of using technology in schools to boost the performance of lower-achieving students. After accounting for family socioeconomic factors (Step 1), student gender was not statistically significant. Variables in the final model accounted for 36.7% of the variance at student level and 18.2% at school level. Hence, the model for primary level had less explanatory power than that for post-primary level, though as with PISA, it does include variables such as confidence in mathematics (the opposite of anxiety about mathematics in PISA). The significance of ESCS in PISA and home resources for learning in TIMSS are indicative of an association between high performance and individual socioeconomic status, even after accounting for other variables.

Interventions

A study by Cullen et al. (2018) aimed to find out what schools in England were doing with the most able disadvantaged pupils at Key Stages 2-4. Earlier research had shown that disadvantaged students in the top 10% at the end of Key Stage 2 (age 11, end of primary school) were less likely than their more advantaged peers to be in the top 10% by the end of Key Stage 4 (ages 14-16 years). A key finding was that successful support for the most academically-able disadvantaged students was not about a single intervention, but about a

suite of activities that, individually and collectively, created a positive impact. In addition to identifying a need for a strong leadership and a strategic focus for this cohort, interventions across four areas were identified as being needed: academic extension; cultural enrichment; personal development; and removal of financial barriers to achievement. Areas of intervention were supported by schools' partnership work with parents, universities, local businesses and others. Monitoring, review and evaluation of outcomes helped schools to focus their efforts on the most cost-effective activities.

According to Montacute (2018), maximising the potential of highly-able young people appears to pose three main challenges for schools: identifying the right students, offering them the right programmes and interventions, and managing the process organisationally in a sustainable way. She also acknowledges that there is currently little evidence on how best to support highly able students, and even less on how to support students who are capable of high attainment who are from disadvantaged backgrounds. However, she states that mentoring and tutoring programmes, and accelerated learning, are interventions which are likely to benefit highly able students. To mitigate against under-identification of highly-able students including those who are socio-economically disadvantaged, she recommends making programmes as widely available as possible, and ensuring that any grouping or targeting is flexible and regularly reassessed. She also notes that the transition from primary to post-primary schooling represents a particular challenge for socio-economically disadvantaged children.

A search of relevant databases was conducted to identify systematic reviews or meta-analyses on addressing the needs of high achievers and/or gifted and talented students in school settings. In all, just 4 studies published since 2011 were identified as being relevant to meeting the needs of higher-achieving students in reading literacy and/or mathematics and related areas. These are summarised in Table 1.

Articles that were excluded, on the basis that they were not directly related to addressing the needs of high achievers or highly-able students in reading literacy and mathematics, included those dealing with perfectionism in academically gifted students (Grugan et al., 2021), and identifying and serving English language learners in gifted education (Mun et al., 2016).

General Reviews of Programme Impact

Drawing on a pool of 557 articles, García-Martínez et al. (2021) identified a final pool of 14 studies, which focused on a variety of didactic strategies and models oriented to meet the

needs of gifted students. These included acceleration, enrichment and extension programmes. They concluded that educational research with gifted population demands more interventions personalised to the specific characteristics of the students. They also saw a need for further research with quasi-experimental designs to identify individualised adaptations focusing on the needs and interests of these students in order to increase their motivation and reduce failure. Concerned with the quality of the research they reviewed, García-Martínez et al. did not report on effect sizes.

Bailey et al. (2012) conducted a systematic review to examine interventions designed to improve the educational achievement of students aged 5-16 years identified as gifted and talented. Based on an initial pool of over 19,000 studies, the authors reduced the final pool to 15, with most of these coming from the US, Australia and the UK. Like García-Martínez et al., Bailey et al. did not report effect sizes, because they were concerned with the quality of some of the studies in their final pool.

With regard to school and classroom organisation, three main settings featured in the studies – selective programmes, sometimes requiring gifted and talented students to change schools; streamed classes, providing gifted and talented students with an enriched environment without changing schools, and mixed-ability classes, catering for gifted and talented students, in the context of a regular classroom. One of the studies (Craven et al., 2000) found that students in special G&T schools and classes experienced greater declines in academic self-concept and motivation, compared with students in streamed and mixed-ability groups. Among the explanations offered for this was the possibility that students in the selective group were negatively affected by change of school or peer group, and that diminished self-concept might have occurred because G&T students were no longer the highest-achieving students in their schools (the ‘Big Fish Little Pond’ effect). Another effective approach identified in Bailey et al.’s review was a ‘vertical curriculum’ version of streaming, where students at both primary- and post-primary levels were allocated to other classes within their school, based on their mathematical ability. Positive effects were also reported for individualised programmes in mathematics, though it was recognised that it might not be possible to provide individualised programmes in all subjects.

Other findings related to:

- The value of teaching specific strategies that enhance G & T students’ learning and engagement (in particular, those developing self-regulation and higher-order thinking skills)

- The important role of the teacher in generating and sustaining the social contexts in which G & T students learn ('careful orchestration of social groupings'), with context often important for academic success and personal motivation.

Bailey et al. noted that, while some positive effects were associated with out-of-school programmes, the fact that they were located outside of school could result in the exclusion of some students. Overall, Bailey et al.'s review supports in-school and in-class approaches to differentiation, with each student, including G & T students, challenged and supported to reach their potential within their mainstream classes, notwithstanding the challenge this may present to schools, given the considerable diversity among G & T students.

Table 1: Tabulation of Systematic Reviews on Effects of Interventions for High-achieving Students

	No. of Studies	Effect Sizes	Key Findings
Bailey, R., Pearce, G., Smith, C., Sutherland, M., Stack, N., Winstanley, C., & Dickenson, M. (2012). Improving the educational achievement of gifted and talented students: a systematic review. <i>Talent Development & Excellence</i> , 4(1), 33-48.	15	No overall average reported	Draws on 15 studies from an initial pool of 19,662 ‘unique’ studies. Examines approaches taken to support G & T students inside and outside the classroom, and largely endorses the approach being implemented in England at the time of writing i.e., efficacy of differentiation within students’ own schools.
García-Martínez, I.; Gutiérrez Cáceres, R.; Luque de la Rosa, A.; León, S.P. (2021). Analysing educational interventions with gifted students. Systematic review. <i>Children</i> , 8, 365.	Sample of 14 studies out of population of 557.	None reported (authors concerned about quality of several of the studies)	The authors concluded that educational research with gifted population demands more interventions personalised to the specific characteristics of the students, as well as stronger research (quasi-experimental designs) to identify quality, not generalised, interventions to meet these needs and replace them with individualised adaptations regarding the needs and interests of these students in order to increase their motivation and reduce failure.
Kim, M. (2016). A Meta-analysis of the effects of enrichment programs on gifted students. <i>Gifted Child Quarterly</i> , 60(2), 102–116.	26 (13 related to academic achievement, and 13 to social-emotional development).	$g = 0.96$ (academic achievement); $g = 0.55$ (socio-emotional development)	Examined enrichment programmes serving gifted students, based on studies published between 1985 and 2014. Significant effects for both academic achievement and socio-emotional development were reported. Where literacy and numeracy are concerned, positive effect sizes were reported for programmes implemented at primary and lower secondary levels. None of the socio-emotional studies focused on
Steenbergen-Hu, S., & Moon, S. M. (2011). The effects of acceleration on high-ability learners: A meta-analysis. <i>Gifted Child Quarterly</i> , 55(1), 39-53.	38, from which 274 effect sizes were extracted. [Early years to college]	$g = 0.18$ (academic achievement) not significant; when one problematic study was removed; this increased to 0.24 and was significant; $g = 0.08$ for social-emotional development.	Examined effects of acceleration on high-ability students’ academic achievement and social-emotional development. High-ability learners were found to benefit from acceleration both in the short-term and in the long run, where academic performance was concerned, while they did as well as or exceeded non-accelerants in social-emotional development (self-concept, self-esteem, self-confidence, social relationships, participation in extracurricular activities, and life satisfaction. No strong evidence regarding moderator effects was found.

Enrichment programmes

According to Kim (2015), “enrichment programmes provide exploratory activities, in-depth materials on a topic, materials for the development of higher-level thinking processes and skills, self-selected independent projects, or authentic produces and services for a real-world audience” (p. 103). She also notes that “enrichment programmes have emphasised the importance of profound knowledge and skills within a subject to develop students’ higher mental processes and creative production” (p. 103). In the context of her meta-analyses of the effects of enrichment programmes on academic achievement and socio-emotional development, Kim referred to an enrichment programme or curriculum as one that had modified content “with more depth or breadth than generally provided, or that had a modified process to develop students’ higher intellectual thinking and to provide opportunities for creative production” (p. 103). Thirteen studies focused on increasing achievement. Among them were studies focusing on enriching reading comprehension and vocabulary (literacy) in grades 5-6, reading and mathematics combined in grades 6-8 and in grade 7 (2 studies), and mathematics achievement (grade 3). All four studies contributed positively to the overall effect size of 0.96 (Hedge’s *g*). Other achievement outcomes that were measured included metacognition, creative abilities and sustained attention. While summer programmes were, on average, more effective than academic year day programmes, there were relatively few of them, and most of the literacy and numeracy programmes fell into academic year day programme category. Kim also examined outcomes for socioemotional programmes but these are not considered here as none focused specifically on attitudes to or self-concept for literacy or numeracy. Kim noted that no high school or upper-secondary programmes were included in her meta-analysis of achievement outcomes, and she attributed this to the widespread use of acceleration programmes (for example, students in upper secondary schools taking university courses) instead at that level. One of the reading literacy programmes that led to strong effects of reading comprehension and vocabulary involved the exploration of complex texts, including *The Odyssey*, *Antigone* and other Greek plays, as well as English classics such as *Beowulf*, *Gilgamesh*, and *The Once and Future King*. Reading comprehension activities focused on developing inference skills and critical reading (Aldrich & Mills, 1999).

Acceleration Programmes

According to Steenbergen-Hu and Moon (2011, p. 39), ‘acceleration is a type of educational intervention based on progress through educational programs either at rates faster than or at

ages younger than one's peers', with the term 'academic acceleration' often used. In their meta-analysis examining the impact of acceleration on high-ability students' academic achievement and social-emotional development² and the difference between content-based and grade-based acceleration, they reported an overall non-significant effect size for achievement ($g = 0.18$). When a problematic study with a substantial negative effect size was removed, the overall effect size increased to 0.24 and was statistically significant. A slightly positive but non-significant effect on social-emotional development (0.076) was also reported. Achievement outcomes included standardized achievement tests, college grades, degrees obtained, status of universities or colleges attended, and career status. Social and emotional outcomes included self-concept, self-esteem, social relationships, participation in extra-curricular activities and life satisfaction. Forms of acceleration included early kindergarten/school/college entrance (14 studies), subject matter acceleration (10), multiple forms (6), advanced placement (2) and curriculum compacting (2), though the authors noted that these were not always unambiguously defined. Moderators such as educational phase (K-12 vs. college) and comparison group (same age, older, mixed-age peers) did not yield significant effect sizes, though effect sizes were more negative than positive for mixed-age group comparisons, and more positive than negative for same-age comparisons. No significant differences between the effects of grade-based and content-based acceleration were reported for academic achievement, possibly because high-ability learners often experience a combination of both types of acceleration over time. Insufficient information was provided to allow the authors to consider effects for high-ability students in different ethnic or socio-economic groups, or different schools types or school environments. Overall, the authors concluded that acceleration does improve high-ability students' academic achievement. Furthermore, they noted that, while overall effect and the effects for moderator analysis for social-emotional development were not significant, they were more promising compared with earlier research.

² Steenbergen-Hu and Moon (2011) describe these as self-concept, self-acceptance, self-reliance, self-esteem, self-confidence, social relationship, participation in extracurricular activities, locus of control, life satisfaction, and educational or vocational plans

Provision and Policy in Ireland

A milestone in acknowledging the needs of gifted and talented students in Ireland was the publication of the *Report of the Special Education Review Committee* in 1993. In the report, a chapter was allocated to the issue of pupils who are ‘exceptionally able or talented’. The report defines these students as ‘those who have demonstrated their capacity to achieve high performance in one or more of the following areas: (a) General intellectual ability; (b) specific academic aptitude; (c) creative or productive thinking; (d) leadership ability; (e) visual and performing arts; (f) mechanical aptitude; and (g) psychomotor ability (e.g., in athletics, gymnastics)’ (p. 160). Although the Review Committee suggested that an IQ score of 130 be denoted as ‘exceptionally able’, they offered the opinion that such adopting such a precise cut-off would ‘have little practical application’ (p. 160). The Committee acknowledged that (at least prior to 1993), students who may be exceptionally able or talented were not formally recognised, but stated that, where such students are formally recognised, a representative range of individual characteristics should be taken into account, including general ability, general achievement and creativity, other behaviours such as work habits and task commitment, and particular talent, as judged by experts in areas such as art, music and athletics. The Committee described three stages involved in identifying and addressing the needs of exceptionally-able and talented students:

- *Screening* – where various in-school procedures are implemented to identify individual differences;
- *Selection* – where schools engage with a selected core group of students to confirm and refine screening results;
- *Differentiation* – where a ‘revolving door’ concept is used to provide activities for exceptionally able and talented students.

The Review Committee noted three approaches then in place to address the needs of exceptionally able and talented at primary level: enrichment (within the existing curriculum), acceleration, and ability-related output, where a common task is assigned, but more is demanded of highly-able students. The Committee pointed to the ‘A’ bands in the State certificate grading system as providing a structure to reflect high student performance. The Committee issued several recommendations, including that:

- Provision for pupils who are exceptionally able or talented should continue to be made in the context of the provision made for the generality of more able pupils within mainstream schools

- School Plans should describe arrangements for the identification and encouragement of pupils who may be exceptionally able or talented
- A named teacher in each school should be responsible for coordinating programmes for pupils who are exceptionally able or talented
- Grant aid should be provided to schools and other organisations which provide enrichment activities for exceptionally able or talented children and young people.

One organisation that has provided relevant support is the Centre for Talented Youth, Ireland at Dublin City University. Established in 1992, the Centre seeks to meet the needs of gifted and talented children between 6 and 17 years of age. Assessment to access courses involves completing tests of abstract reasoning, verbal reasoning and, for older children, numerical reasoning as well. CTY-Ireland's website lists a range of interventions for students at primary and post-primary levels that it organises for those identified as talented including summer programmes, correspondence courses (for primary-level pupils), and early university entrance courses in subjects such as physics, maths, psychology, engineering and Japanese. CTYI also administers a Talent Search to identify and recognise high-ability students in Irish schools. Students who have achieved at or above the 95th percentile on a standardised test are nominated by their schools and receive an award from CTYI (O'Reilly, 2018).

A study involving parents of primary and post-primary students attending courses provided by CTY-Ireland by Cross et al. (2019) painted a generally-negative picture of the ability of schools to cater for gifted students. It was reported that 35% of parents did not know if their child's school had a system in place to identify gifted students, while 55% reported that their school did not have a policy for accelerating high-achieving students. Almost three-quarters reported that their child did not receive differentiated assignments. According to parents, fewer than one-third of their children were being challenged in school (29%), and fewer than a quarter were receiving assignments targeted at their ability level (22%). Seventy percent of parents of primary-level children reported that their child was not being challenged at school. While differentiated assignments were relatively rare, the situation was marginally better at primary than at post-primary level. Virtually all parents opposed grade (class level) acceleration. Echoing the SERC Report, Cross et al. concluded that the primary responsibility for improving the educational experience of high-ability students lies with the schools and hence that professional development for teachers, school leaders and other staff is critical. They recommended a deliberate, planned approach to addressing the needs of gifted students, with schools committed to maximising all students' potential, including that of their most capable students.

The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA), in a collaborative project with the Council for Curriculum, Examinations and Assessment (CCEA) in Northern Ireland, issued draft guidelines in 2007 to support teachers in working with exceptionally able students. The report addressed such issues as definitions, identification, whole-school strategies and classroom strategies. The report estimated that 5-10% of the school-going population ‘might be exceptionally able’ and would be expected to demonstrate advanced attainment in many of the same areas identified in the SERC Report, as well as special abilities in empathy, understanding and negotiation. Reference was made to a subgroup of exceptionally able students – those who are profoundly exceptionally able – estimated to be 0.5% of the school-going population, whose intelligence is in the range of 170+. The report concluded that no one formula could be applied by schools to develop provision of exceptionally able students, ‘with strategies emanating from the strengths of the staff, the needs of the students, and the opportunities that arise from the community activities and personnel involved’ (p. 80). Effective schools were described as those that embraced an ethos that promotes and supports individual differentiation, ‘with careful attention to lesson planning that builds in appropriate challenges for all students’ (p. 80). A survey of school-personnel at primary- and post-primary levels by the NCCA (2008) following publication of the draft guidelines found that they succeeded best in supporting school management and teachers to audit and review school policy and practice. The guidelines were viewed as succeeding less well in supporting management and teachers to differentiate the curriculum, with respondents requesting more examples of differentiation for teaching different age groups and subjects, and concerns expressed by several around the challenges of differentiation. Respondents also called for additional resources, including inservice training, extra teacher allocation, and extra posts of responsibility. In a more recent and larger survey of the same population of school leaders and teachers, Cross et al. (2018) reported that respondents were moderately supportive of special services for gifted students, but were also moderately opposed to grade acceleration, despite research evidence supporting it.

More generally, recent research evidence suggests that progress in addressing the needs of gifted students in Ireland has been slow. In a survey of students certified as gifted by Mensa Ireland, McGrath (2017) reported that such students were not being adequately challenged in school, nor were there adequate resources or additional activities available to address their needs. She also noted that moderate and gradual acceleration were the most popular types of intervention experienced by students, in the form of university classes and fast-paced classes with older advanced students. McGrath noted the underperformance of students from Ireland in the International Mathematical Olympiad, relative to countries with similar average performance in mathematics in the OECD’s Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) as further

evidence of a lack of emphasis in supporting gifted students. In his review of gifted education in Ireland, O'Reilly (2018) noted that the Education for Persons with Special Education Needs Act (ESPEN) in 2004 did not recognise giftedness as a special need. In line with this, he also noted that, in 2016, the national education budget, totalling €9 billion, with €1 billion allocated to special needs, did not allocate any funding to gifted education.

A key source for information for Irish educators may be the website of the National Council for Special Education, which provides information on two broad groups – the exceptionally able (the terms 'gifted' is reserved by the NCES for those with very high IQ scores) and dual exceptionality (where children have both exceptional abilities and severe learning disabilities, or exceptional abilities and poor motivation) (also see Beckman & Minnaert, 2018). The site (ncse.ie) includes a list of national and international organisations that provide supports for children with exceptional abilities. <https://www.sess.ie/categories/exceptionally-able/exceptionally-able>).

The needs of highly-able students more generally have also come to the fore in recent years with concerns about the performance of high achievers (defined as those performing at the highest levels of proficiency on assessments such as the PISA assessment of reading literacy, mathematics and science). In the national report on PISA 2018 for Ireland, for example, it was noted that countries with similar average scores to Ireland in mathematics and science had greater proportions of students performing at the highest proficiency levels, whereas in reading literacy, the proportion of higher performers was broadly along expected lines relative to average performance (McKeown et al., 2019). Students in Ireland in PISA 2018 achieved a mean score (499.6) in PISA mathematics that was significantly higher than the average for OECD countries (489.3), yet just 8.2% of students in Ireland performed at the highest proficiency levels in mathematics (Levels 5-6), compared to 12.9% in the UK, 12.6% in Sweden and 11.6% in New Zealand, all countries with mean scores not significantly different from Ireland's (see Figure 2³). Indeed, among the 10 countries with similar average performance to Ireland in PISA 2018 mathematics, nine had significantly higher proportions performing at Levels 5-6 than Ireland. Furthermore, in Ireland, just 6.6% of females performed at Levels 5-6, compared with 9.9% of males. Corresponding OECD averages were 9.5% and 12.3% respectively. Just 3.7% of students in DEIS schools in Ireland, compared

³ According to McKeown et al. (2019), the countries in Figures 2 and 3 were selected if they were among the highest performers in PISA 2018 mathematics, or if they scored at a level similar to Ireland and were of relevance (due to size, proximity etc.).

with 9.7% in non-DEIS schools achieved at Levels 5-6 (Gilleece et al., 2020). Just 2.2% of females in DEIS schools, compared with 4.5% of males, performed at Levels 5-6.

Figure 2: Percentages of High-Achieving Students on PISA 2018 Mathematics (Proficiency Levels 5-6), Ireland, OECD Average, EU Average and Selected Countries

*Mean score not significantly different from Ireland. Source: McKeown et al. (2019), Figure 3.6

The relative under-performance of high achievers in Ireland in PISA mathematics (and science) contrasts with reading literacy, where Ireland's mean score (518.1) is considerably higher relative to the corresponding OECD average (487.1), and the proportion of students in Ireland (12.1%) performing at proficiency levels 5-6, compares reasonably favourably with other countries with similar average performance to Ireland when measurement error is considered (Figure 3). In Ireland, 10.3% of males and 13.8% of females performed at Levels 5-6. The corresponding OECD averages were 7.1% and 10.4% respectively.

Just 3.7% of students in DEIS schools in Ireland, compared with 9.7% in non-DEIS schools achieved at Levels 5-6 (Gilleece et al., 2020). Just 2.2% of females in DEIS schools, compared with 4.5% of males performed at Levels 5-6. In DEIS schools, 12.1% performed at Levels 5-6, compared with 14.2% in non-DEIS schools. Equivalent percentages of females (5.5%) and males (5.4%) in DEIS schools performed at Levels 5-6.

Figure 3: Percentages of High-Achieving Students on PISA 2018 Reading Literacy (Proficiency Levels 5-6), Ireland, OECD Average, EU Average and Selected Countries

*Mean score not significantly different from Ireland. Source: McKeown et al. (2019), Figure 5.8

Data on high achievement at primary level can be drawn from the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) in which Ireland participates at Grade 4 (and Grade 8) every four years. In TIMSS 2019, students in Ireland ranked in ninth position with 7 countries, including Northern Ireland, achieving significantly higher mean scores (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). Fifteen percent of students in Ireland achieved at the highest TIMSS proficiency level (called the Advanced Benchmark), compared with a TIMSS median of 7%. However, a number of countries had substantially greater proportions of higher achievers compared to Ireland, including Korea (37%), Chinese Taipei (37%), Japan (34%) and Northern Ireland (26%). Figure 4 shows the mean scores and proportions of students performing at the Advanced TIMSS benchmark for the top 10 performing countries at Grade 4 in 2019. While the proportions of higher-achieving students fall as countries' mean scores fall, there are some exceptions to this pattern. Certainly, there is no obvious reason why Ireland lags so far behind Northern Ireland (26% and 15% respectively) with regard to the proportions of students performing at the Advanced level.

Figure 4: Percentages of Students in High-Achieving Countries Performing at the Advanced Benchmark in TIMSS 2019 Mathematics at Grade 4 and Associated Mean Scores

*Mean score not significantly different from Ireland. Source: Mullis et al. (2020).

Like PISA reading literacy in 2018, the most recent results of the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) point to high proportions of high performers in Ireland at primary level. In 2016, Ireland participated in paper-based PIRLS and, along with a subset of countries, in e-PIRLS (an assessment of electronic reading literacy). On paper-based reading, 21% of students in Ireland achieved at the Advanced level. This compared favourably to all but two countries – the highest performing country in the study (Singapore) and the Russian Federation, which had proportions of 54% and 38% respectively (Figure 4). Northern Ireland had 22% of students at Advanced level, but, because of measurement error, this is not significantly different from Ireland. On e-PIRLS 2016, 20% of students in Ireland performed at the Advanced benchmark. This was about the same as in Norway (18%) and the United States (18%), but lagged behind Singapore (36%) (Mullis et al., 2017).

Figure 5: Percentages of Students Performing at the Advanced Benchmark in High-Achieving Countries in PIRLS 2016 Print-based Reading Literacy at Grade 4 and Associated Mean Scores

A number of points arise from these data. First, overall performance in Ireland is better on reading literacy than on mathematics, and this is reflected in the proportions of high performers in reading literacy compared with mathematics (and science). This is also reflected in the relatively large number of comparator countries with higher proportions of students performing at Levels 5-6, compared with Ireland. This points to an important question: Can the performance of higher-achieving students be improved by increasing average performance (i.e., across all students nationally), or should there be a specific focus on better meeting the needs of high performers in domains such as mathematics? If so, a related question is whether this can best be achieved within the confines of the current mathematics syllabi, for example through differentiation, or whether some other approach is required.

Second, as outlined by Pitsia and Lysaght (2021), there is an imperative to improve performance in mathematics and science, arising from government policy in recent years to prioritise STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) subjects. Although policy-related documents such as the *Report of the Stem Education Review Group* (2016) raised the issue of underperformance among high achievers in mathematics (and science) in Ireland, there was no follow-through on this matter in the subsequent Department of Education (2017a) *Policy Statement on Stem Education*. On the other hand, for the first time, specific targets relating to increasing the proportion of high achievers in mathematics (and

science) (those performing at Levels 5-6) were included in the interim review of the *National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy 2011-2020* (DES, 2017b).

Other initiatives, such as the provision of bonus of 25 CAO points for achieving a H6 or better in higher-level Leaving Certificate mathematics (Central Applications Office, 2012) did not specifically address the needs of higher-achieving students as a cohort. For example, the bonus points are unlikely to incentivise students who are likely to perform well on Leaving Certificate mathematics in the first instance (those likely to achieve H1 or H2). One wonders if the mathematic course is sufficiently challenging for such students.

Third, as noted above, there are relatively few high-performing students in DEIS schools. This points to a loss of talent. The lack of higher-achieving female students in DEIS schools is a particular matter of concern. There is a risk, despite the inclusion of targets for increasing the proportions of higher achievers in DEIS schools in assessments such as PISA (see Gilleece et al., 2020), efforts may be expended on raising average performance, or reducing the numbers of lower-achieving students. Although both are worthy goals, there does need to be a stronger focus on higher-achieving students in DEIS schools. In particular, while targets have been set for improving the proportions of students in DEIS schools performing at the highest proficiency levels in national assessments (primary level) and international assessments (post-primary level), no indication is given on how the new targets might be achieved.

Fourth, there is a dearth of higher achievers in Ireland at primary level in TIMSS 2019 mathematics, despite increases in the proportions in Second and Sixth classes achieving Level 4 in the National Assessment of Mathematics between 2009 and 2014 (Shiel et al., 2014), and the relative lack of higher-achieving students seems to carry through to post-primary level. Hence, there may also be value in examining the extent to which the most-able students in mathematics at primary level are supported to reach their potential, and whether such efforts carry through to post-primary level.

Finally, it might be noted that performance on PISA mathematics in Ireland has remained at about the same level across successive cycles between 2003 and 2018, with the exception of 2009, when there was a decline in performance. The implementation of Project Maths does not seem to have made a significant difference to average performance (e.g., Shiel &

A clear message from Pitsia and Lysaght's review of policy initiatives referring to the needs of higher-achieving students in mathematics (and science) is that, despite the desire to improve performance, there are relatively few initiatives in place to do so. On the one hand, it might be assumed that higher level courses in Junior Cycle and Leaving Certificate

Mathematics are sufficiently challenging to propel higher-achievers to greater levels of performance. However, this does not seem to be the case. On the other, as noted by Montacute (2018) and others, relatively little is known about how best to advance the knowledge and skills of higher-achieving students. Based on the reviews in this paper, it is likely that a range of measures, including mentoring and tutoring programmes, differentiation, individualised instruction, and accelerated learning will need to be deployed. One procedure that is not recommended is setting, because highly-able disadvantaged students are less likely to end up in the top sets.

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